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Professional formation and youth insertion on Labor Market in Brazil

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Abstract

Considering that youth insertion on labor Market is a great challenge for the present Society, we are giving continuity with the research in professional and youth insertion on labor Market. On this text, we will present some results of two pieces of research accomplished by doctoral candidates in the Postgraduate Program on Education of Philosophy and Sciences College, Universidade Estadual Paulista, which had as an aim to analyse the process of professional formation of the youth in the state of Ceará, in Brazil, the Project e-Youth and the National Program of Access to Technical Teaching and employment PRONATEC, besides confirming the impact of the courses on the youth insertion on Labor Market after the achievement of the course.

Keywords

education; professional formation; youth and labor in brazil

1. Introduction

Youth insertion on Labor Market is a great challenge for present Society. According to Labor International Organization (VOIT), the world is living one of the worst crisis of youth employment. Between 2007 and 2011, labor and Employment ministry points to that Juvenile unemployment shows its particularities and even in economical growth contexts, remains higher in relation to adult unemployment, at the end of 2017, Labor International Organization (OIT) presents data showing that practically 30% of Brazilian youth would be unemployed, the highest rate since 1991.

Market crisis affects in an uneven way different social groups and regions of Brazil. The unemployment rate is higher for women, youth and low-educated people (IBGE,2017). In front of the social inequalities that permeate Brazilian Society, labor – as a activity strongly articulation to the formation and transformation of the identities of the subjects – shows itself as a problem especially in youth life who live in situation of social vulnerability, for it they do not have access and on it they depend to change their life condition. Through labor, they see the possibility of minimizing the differences and discrimination suffered since birth, in a "rights" deprivation story.

Through the aforementioned problems, which became harder nowadays, we are giving continuity to the research on youth insertion on labor Market, following as well the ways of the professional formation in the country, after changing the government. Here we will present some results of two pieces of research of doctorate, under our orientation, which had the aim to analyse the process of professional formation of youth in the state of Ceará, in Brazil, the project e-youth (e-jovem) and the national Program of Access to Technical Teaching and Employment (Pronatec), besides confirming the impact of these courses on youth insertion on labor Market after the achievement of the course.

1.1. Project e-youth (e-Jovem)

According to Calou (2016), Project e-youth is a public policy implemented with aim to collaborate with the insertion of the youth on the formal professional labor world.

The research was accomplished in capital of the State, Fortaleza and in some towns in the hinterland, where the Project worked since 2007 involving students in an Informatics course. The universe of research comprehended eight groups in towns of hinterland of State; Barro, Crato, Eusébio, Itapoca, Juazeiro do Norte, Granjeiro; one group in the metropolitan area and two groups in Capital – Fortaleza, summing up a total of eight groups and 61 participants.

The specific objectives of the research were to analyse the official documents of the Project and the Pedagogical Practices in the eyes of the students and teachers the used methodology for the collect, treatment and data analysis, was the quantitative-qualitative research of documental and bilbiographical nature with a descriptive approach.

According to the Labor Development Institute (IDT), youth between 15 to 24 years old in the state of Ceará are more penalized by unemployment and face more difficulties of insertion on Labor Market for diverse reasons: lack of experience, inadequate qualification or inexistent qualification, low schooling lack of information on the new models of information, it is the lack of knowledge, in fact, which leaves the youth without alternative of insertion on the world of labor (CALOU, 2016). It was what motivated students to enter the course of Project e-youth 61 answering, 40 (65,6%) answered for “learn informatics”, 17 (27,9%). Seventeen students, 27,9% answered that enrolled in the course to have a profession. Three students, 4,9% looked for the course to be unemployed and just one student stated that wished to do the course to “find a job”.

2. Results concerning to the formation to the world of labor and concerning to the insertion on labor Market

Students stated, in their majority that the course promoted changes, they stated feeling ‘able and in condition to work or set up their own business’. It was the statement of 52 (85,2%) students, just nine (14,8%) tated not feeling prepared.

Corroboration with what the research affirms, after the conclusion of the course, according to Calou (2016) 51 (83,6%) students were working witout working register just 9 (14,8%) students were working formally, reaffirming the labor precariousness of youth. Of these students 26 (42,6%) were working in the field of their formation, in Informatics, however, stated that if wasn’t formal work and some worked as self-employed. Eight students (13,1%) are working in other field and 27 (44,3%) did not answer the question of the sixty-one students that took part in the research, 39 (63,9%) were unemployed and nineteen (31,1%) inserted on labor market, in the field of study.

As it was easy to affirm, by the colected data about students families, many are from very low social economical origin. They had few perspectives of any change in their state of life in country cities, however, with the arrivel of the Project their hopes were renewed and this provoked many expectations for a professional formation.

The Project was developed with pedagogical practices involving new Technologies, building the upknowledge with computer tools besides promoting a colective work, where they socialized their ideas, it solved the group difficulties, clearing doubtts and simulating practical solutions in the net. The first objective of the Project is to make them acquire technical formation, then colaborar to reach a job opportunity, that would represent the access to a professional career. For these reasons, 78,7% of students have affirmed that participating in the Project was very importante for their formation, however, as data show, few got this inserttion in the labor Market in their área of study.

3. National program of access to technical teaching and employment (PRONATEC)

According to Silva (2016) the National Program Access to Technical Teaching and Employment (Pronatec) created in 2011, has as an aim to enable great number of people through the program in order to solve the déficit of qualified professionals to answer labor Market, through free courses in partnership with several institutions that already offered vocational teaching.

Its objectives, also, to increase the number of vacancies in professional and technological education, by means of programs, projects and financial and technical assistance actions. With these objectives, the Program offers technical professional courses of medium level with average duration of one year and a half to two years with workload between 800 and 1200 hours, being able to be coursed in its forms concomitantly, integrated or subsequently to the High School in public schools. The courses offered by Program are free in public institutions, as Federal Network of Professional Education State, districtal and municipal networks of professional education. From 2013 on, private institutions of higher education and technical professional education of high school started to take part in the Program.

The universe of the research was made up by students and participant managers of Pronatec in the courses offered by IFCE – Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Ceará, in the industrial field, at the campi of Fortaleza and Maracanaú (CE). The general purpose was to analyse governmental policy concerning the social-economical-educational, from the eyes of different subjects attained by the Program the specific objectives were; to know the motivations of students who entered the courses in industrial field offered by IFCE at the campi of Fortaleza and Maracanaú; to identify the different perceptions of students and managers during the achievement of these courses; to investigate whether there were significant in a socio-economical level in the life of these youth attained by Pronatec and, too, whether they were inserted on the labor Market after the achievement of this course.

The Methodological procedures the qualitative approach, they were a quiz, interviews and documental analysis. The epistemological current used for the data analysis, collected in the research, was the dialectical materials for according to Gil (2012, p.14) according to this method created by Marx and Engels from Hegel's grounds, social facts cannot be analysed separately from political, economical and cultural influences.

The field of study was the Federal Institute of Science and Technology of Ceará – IFCE at Fortaleza and Maracanaú Campi, with courses in the field of industry. The choice of these campi was due to its geographical location for being in towns where the greatest industrial poles of the state, therefore, there is a bigger professional demand. The technical courses offered by Pronatec are in the field of industry, at Fortaleza campus were: Electrotechnology, Mechanics, Cooling, Workplace Safety. At the Maracanaú Campus the only technical course was industrial automation. Among the participant students 43 students were selected randomly.

4. Results – Youth life after joining a technical course and academical situation after accomplishment of the course.

The majority of students surveyed 96,7% (n=42) related significant changes in their lives after joining a vocational technical course such as Pronatec. The testimonials showed that almost half of the surveyed 47,62% (n=20) considered that the increase of their knowledge and skills in the technological area from Pronatec in the IFCE was a factor that influenced their lives..

The increase of interest of studies represented 19,05% (n=8) of the students surveyed like “student 27” of the automation course “[...] I am more attentive to work that I am going to exercise, I read more articles, magazines and books, and my motivation is each time bigger along with my vision of the future. Some necessary habits not only for being good

professional but for life. The improvement in the personal of Family relationship was pointed by three students as something that changed their lives after joining Pronatec, as highlighted “student 42”.

According to the majority of the answers 72,09% (n=31) there was an intention to work in the field when they finished the course.. Then never stop studying always looking for knowledge. When finished my technical course I want to continue my studies at the college (student 10) “I intend to follow my career in the near factories and later try a higher education: have a better life, for me, my parents and siblings” (student 12).

This perspective to give continuity to studies, is placed by 41,86% (n=18) of the students to show a wish to study in a higher institution to be able to enlarge the range of knowledge in the field..

Concerning the situation of former students, after two years of conclusion of the technical course, we affirmed that 13 (35%) were not working, 15 (37,5%) worked in the field of the course and 11 (12,5%) in another field data that are above data of Brazil in general, given by IBGE. Some of the students complained of the lack of opportunity of employment after the course .

The need to get a job to supply the basic needs, place many youth who have finished the technical course to look for a job also in another field, as we can notice in the speech of the following former students: I have looked for a job for 2 years and the things became hard and then I took what came, it was a job at a gas station (student 7, of the workplace safety course).

We have realized that the education received by these youth of Public Teaching, complemented by professional education, did not make possible in fact a solid formation to enter a place in the Public Higher Education. Concerning insertion on labor Market, also happened that the majority did not get a job, and went to a precarious job. Due to the social-economical reality of some of these youth, there are not many options unless being employed according to their focus on their life reality, as Kuenzer (1992, p.100). It was affirmed what Loponte (2010) said: that the professional education offered to youth, still is very attached to the ideology imposed by capitalism, even in public institutions, as well as in federal institutes, which could offer along with education for work a human formation for citizenship.

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